
The Double-Edged Sword: Investigate the Sino-Indo Relations

¹**Komal**

M.Sc. in Geography, FGM Govt. College, Adampur

²**Surbhi**

M.Sc. in Geography, FGM Govt. College, Adampur

³**Dr. Pawan**

Assistant Professor, FGM Govt. College, Adampur

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15845414>

ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Accepted: 22-06-2025

Published: 10-07-2025

Keywords:

*Geopolitical Strategy,
Religion, Trends,
Diplomatic Relations,
Global Peace.*

ABSTRACT

The present paper examines the dynamics of Sino-Indo relations in terms of their historical roots and contemporary realization. Despite the common characteristics including shared civilizational basis at the foundation of historical relations between these two fast-growing Asian superpowers, the current estrangement and widespread diplomatic tensions make their relations appear to be a 'double-edged sword' which is a burning issue for geopoliticians and academics. Recognizing the importance of the global issue, which is also important for international peace, a comprehensive review of existing literature was carried out and secondary source data was used. In the Global Peace Report, a significant increase has been found in the peace index investigation of both the countries individually. But the deterioration in relations between the two countries is clearly highlighted due to the tension arising in border conflicts, trade volume, cultural relationship, infrastructure development and other aspects. The study suggests that there is a need to focus on platforms such as open communication, promoting cultural and ethical interactions for global peace, sustainable development and strong Indo-Sino relations.

Introduction:

India and China, two ancient civilizations and modern powerhouses, share a relationship marked by deep historical ties, economic interdependence, and strategic rivalry. From cultural exchanges through Buddhism to border disputes and power struggles in the Indo-Pacific, their interactions have shaped Asia's geopolitical landscape (Arif S., 2015 and Singh T. & Birendri, 2023). Economic relations remain a crucial aspect, with China being one of India's top trading partners. However, concerns over trade deficits and strategic projects like the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) continue to impact bilateral ties (Zilong, 2021). Border tensions remain a flashpoint. A key factor in this tension is Tibet which remain under China's control, making India's long and sensitive border with a region a source of strategic concern. Despite agreements like the Panchsheel Treaty and Confidence Building Measures Agreement (CBMs), clashes such as the Galwan Valley incident show deep-seated mistrust (Rajagopalan R. & Prasad K., 2010). In the Indian Ocean, China's "String of Pearls" strategy—building ports in Sri Lanka, Pakistan, and Myanmar—seeks to encircle India. In response, India strengthens its "Necklace of Diamonds" strategy, forging military and economic ties with Japan, Australia, and Southeast Asia. This maritime chess game defines their regional contest for influence (Mengal J., 2022). Despite these challenges, India and China continue to engage in diplomatic forums such as BRICS and the Shanghai Cooperation Organisation (SCO), recognizing the importance of maintaining regional stability (Gokhale, 2022). The future of their relationship will depend on how both nations navigate economic ties, border disputes, and geopolitical competition while seeking areas of mutual cooperation. (Ratha K. & Mahapatra S, 2014).

Objective- To investigate the shape and trends of Indo-China relationship in historical perspective and contemporary scenarios.

Methodology- The present paper uses secondary data sources which include published books, academic journals, official reports and credible online articles. The present objectives examine the relations between India and China by adopting historical, empirical and descriptive approaches to comprehensively review the existing literature for in-depth analysis. To identify the peace levels of India and China separately, data from the Institute of Economic and Peace (2018 to 2024) has been used. The trends of trade as well as peace and other parameters have been displayed by line, bar graphs and flow charts. To examine the bilateral trade pattern between India and China, data published by the Department of Commerce, Ministry of Commerce and Industry, India has been used.

Result and Discussion: -**Parameter to evaluate Indo-China relationship:**

The Indo-China relationship can be evaluated through multiple dimensions, including;

1). Border Issues

India shares the second longest land border with China after Bangladesh (3,488 km, according to the Ministry of Home Affairs). The LAC (Line of Actual Control) serves as the boundary between these two countries. The lack of proper demarcation of the India-China border has often resulted in clashes between the armies of the two sides. This parameter examines conflicts in three sectors of the border (Western, Central and Eastern) and how they impact warlike situations and current relations between India and China.

i. Western sector- This part between the two countries lies mainly along the eastern Ladakh region (1597 km). The Johnson Line and the McDonald Line are two proposed boundary lines for the disputed region of Aksai Chin. The Johnson Line was proposed in 1865 by British surveyor Sir Henry Johnson. The line he proposed showed that Aksai Chin was part of India's Kashmir region. India later referred to this line as the basis for its territorial claim over Aksai Chin, which China still disputes. The second, the Macartney-MacDonald Line was proposed in 1899 by Lord Macartney and Sir Charles MacDonald, who

suggested that Aksai Chin should be considered part of China's territory. China uses this McDonald Line as one of its claims over Aksai Chin, especially after the 1962 Sino-Indian War.

Major clashes:

- 1962 (Sino-India War)- In 1950s China built G219 highway that connects Xinjiang with Tibet, cutting across Aksai Chin. Furthermore, China shows Aksai Chin in his political map which India discovered in 1957. India opposed it, but China ignored it. This led to rising tension between the two nations. In 1961-62, India adopted the Forward Policy and established its outposts close to China. China considered this a provocative action and responded by attacking. India faced defeat in the war. China captured Aksai Chin, which is still under its control today.
- In the 2013 clash - when the Chinese army entered about 19 km inside the DBO (Daulat Beg Oldi) area of Ladakh and set up their tents. India retaliated by sending the ITBP and the Army to set up their camp about 300 meters away, which created a situation of tension. India held diplomatic and military level talks. Three weeks later, the Chinese army removed their tents and retreated. After this incident, India increased its patrolling in the area.
- In the 2020 clash- India was building the Darbuk-Shyok-Daulat Beg Oldi (DSDBO) road which was opposed by China. Also, China started building infrastructure in the area that India claims as its own. Therefore, India increased its military presence. The tension in the Galwan Valley led to a crucial military meeting on June 6, where both sides agreed to withdraw troops and create a buffer zone. However, on June 15, Indian troops found that China had not completely withdrawn its forces. This led to a face-off between Indian and Chinese troops in the Galwan Valley.

ii. Middle sector- It is mainly a border with Uttarakhand (345 km) and Himachal (200 km). It is a relatively peaceful area compared to other border areas. The Himachal Pradesh border has not been a hotspot for violent clashes, while there are occasional standoffs between patrols, but it is handled under the border management protocols. India built a road to the Lipu-Lekh pass in 2020 which was opposed by China. However, the incident was resolved through diplomatic talks and not direct military clashes.

iii. Eastern Sector- It passes through Sikkim (220 km) and Arunachal Pradesh (1126 km). The boundary between Arunachal Pradesh and Tibet (China) was demarcated by British India's Foreign Secretary Sir Henry McMahon at the Shimla Conference of 1914. India recognises this as the official boundary but China claims Arunachal Pradesh as "South Tibet". China did not consider Sikkim to be part of India. In 1975, India made Sikkim its 22nd state, which China rejected as illegal. In 2003, both countries took

positive steps and discussed resolving the border dispute, resulting in a joint statement by India and China in 2005 in which China for the first time officially recognised Sikkim as part of India.

Major clashes-

- In 1959, Zhou Enlai declared the McMahon Line illegal, stating that it was imposed on them by the British. China claimed that Arunachal Pradesh (then the North-East Frontier Agency, NEFA) was its territory. This dispute became one of the main reasons for the 1962 India-China war. India gave statehood to Arunachal Pradesh in 1987.
- 1975- India and China's border troops engaged in a violent clash at Tulong La Pass (Arunachal Pradesh). In 1975, Chinese soldiers attacked a unit of Indian soldiers. It was the last violent clash between them before the 2020 incident.
- 1967- The Nathu La clashes occurred when the Chinese Army attacked the Indian post at Nathu La, which was a part of Sikkim, a region under India's sovereignty at that time but China didn't accept it.
- 2017- Doklam Standoff - Doklam is a plateau located at the tri-junction of India, Bhutan and China. This area is claimed by both Bhutan and China, but India supports Bhutan's claim due to their close diplomatic relations and strong military ties. In June 2017, China started constructing a road in Doklam, which gives it easier access to the Siliguri corridor, making India's Northeast State at risk in case of conflict. Since Bhutan does not have a strong military, India intervened, send military forces to stop this construction. This led to a 73 days stand-off. In August 2017, both countries agreed to disengage after intense diplomatic talks. China stopped the road construction, but the tension over the region remains.

India and China have diplomatic relations to some extent, but due to past conflicts, there is still a lack of trust between them.

2). Economic Aspect- India and China are two of the world's largest economies, with a long trading history with each other. Their mutual economic relations are affected by various factors such as trade imbalances, border issues and policies.

Trade between India and China began with the Silk Road, which connected East Asia and South Asia to Europe. India exported spices, cotton, ivory and textiles to China, while China sent silk, ceramics and paper. In the 18th century, the British forced Indians to cultivate opium, which they exported to China. China exported products such as tea and silk to Britain, while Britain sent industrial textiles to India.

This created the Opium Triangle Trade. After independence, trade between the two countries was limited. After the Panchsheel Agreement, trade cooperation between the two countries improved. India exports raw materials while China sends manufactured goods. After the Sino-Indian War of 1962, trade suffered a major setback. Actual trade cooperation began after the Prime Minister's visit to China in 1988, when he established the Joint Economic Group (JEG). It is seen as the foundation of modern economic cooperation.

The India-China Strategic and Economic Dialogue (SED) was established in December 2010 to address macroeconomic issues, domestic economic challenges and enhance mutual cooperation. It was aimed at taking steps through discussions to resolve trade issues between the two countries.

Several Indian banks, including SBI (Shanghai), Bank of India (Shenzhen), Canara Bank (Shanghai) and Bank of Baroda (Guangzhou), have opened branches in China, wherein SBI was authorised to conduct RMB (Renminbi) denominated business. On the other hand, China's ICBC (Commercial Bank of China) got a licence to operate in India. Due to the growing trade relations between India and China, companies from both countries have strengthened their presence in each other's markets.

Bilateral Trade Volume- The total trade of these two countries between April and November 2024 is 83.63 US billion dollar, which is 11.05 percentage of total trade of India. India export goods worth of 9,210.60 US million dollar to China, representing 3.25 percent of total export (283,69.5 US million dollar) with China ranking as the 6th largest export destination. India imports goods worth of 74,415.01 US million dollar from China, making China the top importer to India with 15.75 percent of total import (472,33.61 US million dollar).

India and China Bilateral Trade (in USD Bn)							
Years	India's export to China	Percent change	India's import from China	Percent change	Trade deficit	Total trade	Percent change
2016	8.96	-7.63	60.65	-0.74	51.69	69.61	-1.68
2017	12.66	41.29	72.04	18.78	59.38	84.7	21.68
2018	16.49	30.25	73.87	2.54	57.38	90.36	6.68
2019	17.12	3.82	68.35	-7.47	51.23	85.47	-5.41
2020	18.95	10.69	58.71	-14.10	39.76	77.66	-9.14
2021	23.05	21.64	87.65	49.29	64.6	110.7	42.54
2022	15.15	-34.27	102.63	17.09	87.48	117.78	6.40
2023	16.23	7.13	99.59	-2.96	83.36	115.82	-1.66

(Source: Department of Commerce, Ministry of Commerce and Industry, India)

India and China experienced strong trade growth from 2016 to 2018. India's exports increased by 41.29 percent in 2017 and 30.25 percent in 2018. The increase in trade was driven by rising demand for Chinese electronics, machinery and chemicals in India and China's import of Indian cotton and iron ore. In 2021, as both economies recovered from the pandemic, trade rebounded sharply, with India's exports rising by 21.64 percent and imports from China surging by 49.29 percent, pushing total trade to a record \$110.7 billion. The trade growth highlighted India's dependence on Chinese imports, widening the trade deficit and emphasizing the need for a balanced trade relationship.

India- China trade imbalance- In 2022-23, India faced a trade deficit with China. The gap between India's imports and exports with China reached nearly \$100 billion.

Reason for trade deficit- China's cost-effective manufacturing and advanced supply chains make its products more affordable for Indian businesses. Due to limited domestic high-tech production, India depends heavily on Chinese imports to meet demand.

Government Actions India's "Make in India" initiative aims to boost domestic manufacturing, but progress has been slow. Instead of strict import restrictions, India should focus on strengthening its manufacturing sector to achieve sustainable economic growth.

BRI And CPEC- China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) aims to increase global trade through land and sea routes, but India opposes it due to sovereignty concerns over the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) that passes through PoK. India also sees the BRI as a geopolitical strategy to challenge China's growing influence and its own regional interests.

India and China share a strong but unbalanced economic relationship, with India heavily dependent on Chinese imports. Strengthening domestic manufacturing and addressing trade disparities are key to a more stable and mutually beneficial partnership. India is trying to reduce its dependence on Chinese products and investments by promoting local industries and building stronger trade ties with other countries.

3). Historical and Cultural Relationship- The relationship between India and China was not just about trade or politics; it was a rich and long-lasting exchange of ideas, beliefs, and creativity.

Indian monks like Kashyapa Matanga, Dharmaratna, Kumarajiva, Bodhidharma, and Dharmakshema spread Buddhism in China, while Chinese monks like Fa Xian and Xuan Zang travelled to India to extend their Buddhist studies. Both civilizations exchanged knowledge in astronomy, mathematics, and medicine, enriching each other's traditions.

In 2003, Peking University set up a Centre for Indian Studies to promote research on Indian history, culture, and relations with China. Several universities, including Shenzhen University, Jinan University, Fudan University, Guangdong University, and Shanghai International Studies University, have also introduced Indian Studies and Hindi language programs to strengthen cultural and academic ties between the two countries.

In 2010, India built a Buddhist temple at the White Horse Temple complex in Luoyang to honour Kashyapa Matanga and Dharmaratna. In 2007, the Xuanzang Memorial was opened in Nalanda. In 2008,

India and China issued joint stamps featuring the Mahabodhi Temple in Bodh Gaya and the White Horse Temple in Luoyang.

Bollywood films have had an influence on Chinese culture, becoming popular in the 1960s and 1970s and continuing to gain popularity in current years.

The Swami Vivekananda Cultural Center (SVCC), established in 2018 in Beijing, plays an important role in promoting Indian culture through yoga, dance, music, and Hindi language programs.

In 2021, the Indian Embassy organized Diwali and Dussehra events with food stalls, exhibitions, and performances. In 2023, Beijing will host a Spring Fair with Indian handicrafts, food, music, and dance as central attractions.

The Mahabharata mentions China several times, including the mention of Chinese people bringing gifts during the Pandavas' Rajasuya Yagna. Some historians said that Chinese culture is influenced by Indian Vedic culture. The word "Mandarin" is derived from the Sanskrit word "mantra". Some Chinese scholars tried to incorporate Sanskrit phonetics into the Chinese language. Indian texts were translated into Chinese, introducing new ideas and literary styles. Currently, the centre is located near Dharamsala, from where he leads the Tibetan government in exile. His stay in India caused tensions between India and China, as China saw it as interference in its affairs.

Although India-China relations have sometimes been strained over the Tibet issue, the two countries have always been culturally connected and have good cultural ties.

4.) Political and International Policies:

4.1 Indo-China Agreements:

India and China formulate policies from time to time to improve their relations. Some of them are explained below.

Panchsheel Agreement (April 1954)- The Panchsheel Agreement was a promise made by India and China to treat each other as equals and respect each other's territory. It had five main principles:

- a) Mutual respect for each other's territorial integrity and sovereignty.
- b) Mutual non-aggression.
- c) Mutual non-interference in each other's internal affairs.

- d) Equality and mutual benefit.
- e) Peaceful coexistence.

In December 1988 India and China decided to set up two groups to improve their relations. Joint Working Group (JWG) on Boundary Issue - This group was created to find a fair and peaceful solution to the long-standing border dispute between India and China. Joint Group on Trade, Economy and Science - This group was created to help the two countries work together in trade, commerce and scientific research, indicating that they wanted to focus on more than just the boundary issue. In 1993, India and China signed an important agreement to maintain peace and stability on the Line of Actual Control (LAC). The aim of this agreement was to prevent conflicts and resolve border issues through peaceful means. Key Provisions of this agreement are:

- a) Recognition of LAC – Both countries acknowledged the existence of the LAC and agreed to maintain peace along it.
- b) No Use of Force – Both sides agreed not to use military force to settle border disputes.
- c) Military Control Measures – Both nations agreed to limit troop deployment and military exercises near the border.
- d) Diplomatic Engagement – Regular talks at diplomatic and military levels were planned to address disputes.
- e) Dispute Resolution Mechanism – Both sides decided to resolve issues through dialogue rather than conflict.

The 1996 CBM Agreement between India and China was signed to strengthen the 1993 Border Peace and Tranquillity Agreement. Key Provisions of this agreement

- a) Limited Troop Deployment – Both nations agreed to reduce and regulate military presence near the LAC.
- b) No Use of Force – Both sides committed not to use or threaten to use force in border disputes.
- c) Restrictions on Military Exercises – Any large-scale military exercises near the border required prior notification to the other side.
- d) Airspace Management – Both countries agreed not to fly combat aircraft within 10 km of the LAC.
- e) Communication and Cooperation – Mechanisms for regular dialogue and border meetings were established to prevent misunderstandings.

- f) Border Management Protocols – Both sides agreed to respect each other's patrols and avoid aggressive actions.

The 2005 Special Representatives mechanism helped India and China talk about their border issues, but the dispute is still unresolved and requires further discussions.

The Border Defence Cooperation Agreement 2013 between India and China aimed to prevent military tensions along the LAC through communication, trust building and conflict prevention. It emphasized on respecting the border, avoiding patrol clashes, maintaining military dialogue, preventing airspace violations and resolving disputes peacefully without the use of force.

Wuhan Spirit (2018) The aim of the delegations of the two countries in Wuhan was to reduce tensions between India and China by better understanding, improving communication and working together peacefully and strengthen relations.

4.2 International Organisations:

BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, South Africa) is a group of major emerging economies representing 40 percent of the world's population formed to promote economic and political cooperation and aims to reform global financial systems. BRICS serves as a platform for India and China to cooperate economically, but their ongoing territorial disputes and geopolitical rivalry continue to create tensions below the surface. The Shanghai Cooperation Organisation (SCO), formed in 2001, promotes security, trade, and regional cooperation. Its members include China, Russia, India, Pakistan, and Central Asian countries. The SCO focuses on combating terrorism, promoting trade, and strengthening political ties. India and China agreed to resume patrolling and grazing in Depsang and Demchok by October 2024, as they were before the tensions.

Quad (Quadrilateral Security Dialogue)- The Quad is a group of four countries – India, the US, Japan and Australia – that work together on security and regional issues, primarily in the Indo-Pacific region. India joined the Quad to counter China's growing influence, especially in the Indian Ocean through a security perspective. Act East Policy (1990)- A policy proposed by India whose main goal is to improve trade, cultural and strategic relations with Southeast Asian and East Asian countries. This helps India to reduce China's influence in the region by building strong ties with countries like Vietnam, Japan and Indonesia. It also supports infrastructure projects like the India-Myanmar-Thailand highway to improve regional connectivity. China sees this policy of India as a challenge to its dominance in Asia. India's growing

involvement with the US, Japan and Australia through the Quad has increased tensions with China. Both the Quad and Act East Policy help India protect its interests in the Indo-Pacific.

4.3 Strategies Adopted by Both Countries:

The "String of Pearls" theory refers to China's strategy of developing ports and infrastructure in countries surrounding India, such as Sri Lanka, Pakistan, and Myanmar-seeks to encircle India. This network of strategic locations helps China secure its trade routes and expand its influence in the Indian Ocean.

Necklace of Diamonds is India's counter-strategy to China's String of Pearls, aiming to prevent Chinese encirclement. India achieves this by:

- a) Strategic Partnerships – Strengthening ties with Vietnam, Japan, the Philippines, and Australia.
- b) Naval Expansion – Securing access to ports like Chabahar (Iran), Sabang (Indonesia), and Duqm (Oman).
- c) Indian Ocean Presence – Enhancing cooperation with Seychelles, Mauritius, and Madagascar.
- d) Military & Surveillance – Deploying radar systems and increasing maritime security in key locations. This ensures India's security, trade dominance, and strategic balance in the Indo-Pacific.

The "salami slicing" strategy refers to China's gradual, incremental actions to assert control over disputed territories without provoking major opposition. In the South China Sea, this was evident on March 9, 2014, when China's coast guard blocked Philippine boats from resupplying troops at the Second Thomas Shoal, accusing them of strengthening territorial claims. China employs this strategy by making small moves—such as building structures or increasing military presence—that individually seem minor but collectively enhance its control over the region. Pangda's, a village, development near Doklam reflects China's "salami slicing" strategy, gradually expanding control through small and incremental.

China's "Five Fingers of Tibet" strategy, views Tibet as the "palm" and Ladakh, Nepal, Sikkim, Bhutan, and Arunachal Pradesh as its "fingers." This concept suggests that China sees these regions as historically linked to Tibet and aims to extend its influence over them. The strategy reflects China's broader territorial ambitions in the Himalayan region, influencing its policies and border disputes with India and neighbouring countries.

India-China relations are shaped by cooperation and competition, marked by agreements like Panchsheel, BRICS, and SCO for diplomacy and trade, alongside border disputes, China's String of Pearls, and India's Necklace of Diamonds strategy to counter Chinese influence in the Indo-Pacific.

5.) Infrastructure-

Infrastructure plays a crucial role in shaping India-China relations, impacting trade, security, and regional influence. It serves as both a tool for cooperation and a source of conflict between the two nations.

1. **Border Infrastructure & Security- China's Strategy:** China has developed extensive railways, highways, and airports in Tibet to strengthen its presence along the Indian border. The Lhasa-Nyingchi Railway (2021) improves troop movement near Arunachal Pradesh. Such developments increase India's security concerns. **India's Response:** India has accelerated border road construction, including the Darbuk-Shyok-DBO Road in Ladakh and the Atal Tunnel (2020) to improve military access. Infrastructure competition has increased tensions, leading to standoffs like the Galwan clash (2020).

2. **Trade & Connectivity China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI):** China's massive infrastructure project aims to enhance global connectivity, but India opposes it due to the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) passing through Pakistan-occupied Kashmir (PoK). **India's Alternatives:** India is investing in Chabahar Port (Iran) and the International North-South Transport Corridor (INSTC) to counter China's growing regional influence. However, Chinese investments in South Asian infrastructure give it an edge in regional trade.

3. **Water & Hydropower Infrastructure- China's Dams on Brahmaputra:** China has built multiple hydropower projects like Zangmu (2015) and Jiacha (2020) in Tibet, raising concerns about water flow control. India fears water diversion during dry seasons or sudden releases causing floods. **India's Response:** India is strengthening hydropower projects in Arunachal Pradesh to assert its rights over Brahmaputra water. The lack of a water-sharing treaty makes infrastructure a critical factor in this dispute.

4. **Digital & Technological Infrastructure- Chinese Tech in India:** Chinese firms like Huawei and ZTE were deeply involved in India's telecom sector, but security concerns after the 2020 border clashes led India to restrict them from 5G expansion. India is investing in semiconductor manufacturing and indigenous 5G networks to reduce dependence on Chinese technology.

Trends of International Peace:

The Global Peace Index (GPI) ranks countries based on factors like safety, ongoing conflicts, and militarization. Over the past seven years, China maintains its lead, but India shows stronger improvement

in GPI rankings. India's GPI rank has shown steady improvement, while China's progress has been more inconsistent. India started with small gains, faced a setback in 2019, and then gradually improved, with its most significant rise in 2024. In contrast, China initially

improved but saw declines in 2020 and 2021 before making a strong recovery in 2022 and 2023. However, in 2024, China's rank dropped again, while India continued to improve. Overall, India has made more consistent long-term progress, whereas China, despite its better ranking, has experienced fluctuations. If this trend continues, India may further close the gap in global peace rankings.

Suggestion/ Recommendation-

- To improve India-China relations, both countries need to focus on open communication to resolve border disputes peacefully and regularly hold high-level talks.
- Both the countries should implement their existing agreement effectively to improve the relation and to reduce tension.
- Increasing trade and investment opportunities can strengthen economic relations. Efforts to balance trade and collaborate in technology and manufacturing sectors will be beneficial.
- Promoting cultural interactions, educational partnerships, and tourism can help in understanding each other's cultures better and reducing misconceptions.
- In sensitive issues, involving neutral third-party mediators can help in building trust and resolving conflicts peacefully.

Conclusion- India and China share a complex relationship marked by both cooperation and competition. Historically connected through culture and trade, recent border disputes have strained ties. Despite tensions from incidents like the Doklam standoff, Galwan valley clash, and issues like the Brahmaputra dams and BRI, they continue diplomatic talks and trade. In the Global Peace Report, a significant increase has been found in the peace index investigation of both the countries individually. But the deterioration in relations between the two countries is clearly highlighted due to the tension arising in border conflicts, trade volume, cultural relationship, infrastructure development and other aspects. In nut shell, their future relations depend on how they manage conflicts and collaborate on common interests.

References-

- Singh S, 2008, India-China Relations: Perception, Problems, Potential, South Asian Survey 15 (1) 83–98.
- Mukherjee & Malone, 2010, India and China: Conflict and Cooperation, Survival, Vol. 52, No. 1, pp. 137–158.
- Das N., 2013, India-China Relations: A New Paradigm, Institute for Defence Studies and Analyses, No. 19.
- Arif S., 2015, A history of Sino-Indian relations: From Conflict to Cooperation, Prime Scholar Library, Vol. 3 (3), pp. 110-118.
- Badatya S. 2018, Border Disputes, War and the changing Dynamics of India’s China Policy, The Journal of Central Asian Studies, Vol. XXV.
- Mehta & Dar, 2020, A study of India China trade relations, International Journal of Political Science and Governance, 2 (2): 10-14.
- Gokhale 2022, A Historical Evaluation of China’s India Policy: Lessons for India-China Relations Carnegie Endowment for International Peace.
- Shamim & Khan, 2022, China-India Relations: A Critical Analysis of Convergence and Divergence, Orient Research Journal of Social Sciences June, 2022, Vol.7, No. 1 14-22.
- Ogden C, 2022 The Double- Edged Sword: Reviewing India–China Relations, India Quarterly 78 (2) 210–228.
- Birendri & Singh, 2023, India-China Relations Since Post Independence: Challenges and Future Prospects, Juni Khyat, Vol-13, Issue- 01.